

WHAT IS BRIDGE?

Bridging Science and Local Communities to wildfire risk reduction, is a research project that began on March 15, 2021, funded by the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) under the call for Scientific Research and Technological Development Projects on Prevention and Fighting of Forest Fires.

People

Promote dialogue in risk management

Forest

Land uses and landscape management

House

Ways of adapting

Wildfire Risk

Wildfire risk reduction

INNO LAB

The Innovation Lab (InnoLab) aims to create a collaborative learning space for sharing different knowledge, visions and experiences on Monchique. On this InnoLab session, dialogue was encouraged between the community, organizations, local government and scientists involved in forest fire risk management.

Objective: Develop collaboratively a **community vision of the Monchique forest** to promote dialogue on **wildfire risk prevention**.

Session: 19 of may 2022, Monchique.

Audience: Representatives of local institutions/entities, owners and residents of Monchique.

Method: Participants were asked to answer 4 questions. The exercises address past, present and future, promoting the construction of a community vision of the Monchique forest.

SHARED COMMUNITY VISION

RESULTS

...**Fire resilience**, a healthy and sustainable village, a territory that is more ordered and resilient territory, with integrated management

Why? Low resilience to fire events, need to improve fuel management areas

How? Adapt the Legal Framework to the specificity of each territory, create a "Simplex" for the rural territory, promote sustainable management and a greater relationship between rural spaces and urban centers

...**Biodiverse agro-forestry mosaic**, with protection and production zones in harmony
Less fragmented landscape that remunerates ecosystem services

Why? Fragmentation of the landscape, extension of eucalyptus monoculture, abandonment of the forest

How? Creating a forest defense network against fires, valuing services and promoting ecosystem longevity. Recovering the know-how of the old ones.

...Better **accessibility networks and infrastructure**, without motorized vehicles and gas stations

Why? Lack of accessibility and infrastructure

How? Improving public mobility/transport and communication network

...**Economic Dynamics**, greater number and diversification of companies, independence from financial subsidies and tourism focused on nature and customs

Why? Difficulty in investing on the territory and in creating new jobs/businesses

How? Promoting leisure and economic activities, valuing endogenous products, creating employment and diversifying productive activities

...**Population**, dynamic and more populated society, with social valorization and Education linked to the forest and industries

Why? Populational aging, lack of professional training and human desertification

How? Capacitating population, increasing the housing supply, Strengthening education, secondary and vocational, and the health system

